

Reproducing: Do Simpler Statistical Methods Perform Better in Multivariate Long Sequence Time-Series Forecasting?

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The goal is to reproduce the experiments of the paper "Do Simpler Statistical Methods Perform Better in Multivariate Long Sequence Time-Series Forecasting?". Although there is not all needed information available, it is possible to achieve similar results after further researching and trying different model assumptions.

CCS Concepts: • **Mathematics of computing** → **Probability and statistics**.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: Time-series forecasting; deep learning; statistical methods

1 INTRODUCTION

This report summarizes the results of trying to reproduce the paper "Do Simpler Statistical Methods Perform Better in Multivariate Long Sequence Time-Series Forecasting?" [4]. This paper uses SNaive, which is a simple model taken seasonality into consideration, and linear regression to perform multivariate long sequence time-series forecasting. On eight benchmark datasets they show that those two simple models perform better than some deep learning methods with the performance measures MSE and MAE. In the paper it is also shown, that the error upper bound of linear regression is $o(n)$ for multivariate long sequence time-series forecasting.

We try to reproduce this work, starting with describing the experimental setup of the paper in Section 2. Moreover, the datasets, which are used, are described as well as the papers from which the deep learning methods and results are taken from. The next part of our report, Section 3, states our reformulations of the models, which are illustrated on some small examples. This section also includes the formulas for the MSE and MAE, which we use. After that all parameters and the results are summarized. Section 4 states the difficulties, which we faced in the reproducing process. The last section includes our conclusion.

2 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The hypothesis of the paper is "Do linear regression and SNaive perform better than some deep learning methods?". Therefore, the linear regression and the SNaive models are the independent variables of the experiment and the MSE and MAE or the performance indicators which are the dependent variables. The control is to compare the results of the models used in the paper to the results of other deep learning methods, which already calculated the MSE and MAE for the used datasets. To test the hypotheses, the linear regression and SNaive models are implemented and tested on eight benchmark datasets for multivariate long sequence time-series forecasting. The resulting MSE and MAE are compared to the other models if they perform better or are at least under the best three models for each dataset.

2.1 Datasets

We shortly describe the eight datasets which were used to test the models. There are three ETT datasets, which collect electricity transformer temperature data for different time levels (1 hour and 15 minutes) and two counties of China [8]. Then there is a dataset about electricity consuming load (ECL) of some clients [8]. The next dataset

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WTH contains hourly weather data from the USA [8]. Another weather dataset (Weather) contains meteorological indicators in 10 minute intervals [7]. The ILI dataset records weekly influenza-like patients data [7]. The last dataset Exchange includes daily data about exchange rates of eight countries [7].

2.2 Cited models

To be able to compare the resulting MSE and MAE of Linear Regression and SNaive on the datasets already existing results for the datasets with other models are used. Deep learning methods which are RNN-based, CNN-based or Transformer-based are stated. There is the LSTMa [1], Reformer [2], LSTNet [3], LogTrans [5], TCN and SCINet [6], Autoformer [7], Informer [8]. The resulting MSE and MAE for this methods and the datasets are listed in the papers [6], [7], [8].

3 REPRODUCING THE PAPER

This chapter summarizes our understanding of the paper, reformulating the main ideas of the paper. All difficulties and possible differences that we came across in that process are stated in section 4.

The problem of multivariate long sequence time-series forecasting is to predict a horizon h of more than 24 steps into the future for d variables, $d > 1$, at the same time. We use n past time steps to predict and T is the time span of the whole dataset.

3.1 Models

For linear regression we fit d independent models, which are separate models for each feature. In the following, X is the input matrix for one feature. We split the original data into a train and test set by a factor f . The resulting train set has the length $N = T \cdot f$ and the test set $T - N$. Since we use a sliding window method the input matrix rows $X_i \in \mathbb{R}^n$ are defined with the following formula, where $D \in \mathbb{R}^T$ is the original data column of one feature:

$$X_i = (D_i, \dots, D_{i+n-1})^T (i = 1, \dots, N - n - (h - 1)) \quad (1)$$

The input matrix has $N - n - (h - 1)$ rows, because the sliding window has size n and we want to predict h values and $n + h$ can exactly be placed $N - n - (h - 1)$ times in the training data which has the size N . We regress on Y , where one row Y_i is defined with:

$$Y_i = (D_{i+n}, \dots, D_{i+n+h-1})^T (i = 1, \dots, N - n - (h - 1)) \quad (2)$$

The dimension of Y is then $(N - n - (h - 1)) \times h$. Then regression with multiple target variables can be applied by $Y \sim X$, this can also be seen as h separate models, i.e. one model for each step in the horizon.

With the regression for every feature we get the coefficient matrix $(\theta^1, \dots, \theta^h)$, where $\theta^i \in \mathbb{R}^n (i = 1, \dots, h)$. With this matrix we can predict h values into the future with n given input rows, which can be shifted to be able to predict everything in the test set.

The prediction matrix \hat{Y} for one feature has the following form for one row \hat{Y}_M , when we assume that the values up to timepoint M are known and we want to predict h values into the future:

$$\hat{Y}_M = (D_{M-n+1} \cdot \theta_1^1 + \dots + D_M \cdot \theta_n^1, \dots, D_{M-n+1} \cdot \theta_1^h + \dots + D_M \cdot \theta_n^h)^T (M = N, \dots, T - h) \quad (3)$$

This works for $H = (T - N) - (h - 1)$ times, which is the test set length minus $(h-1)$. We use these H predictions for calculating the MSE and MAE later. For better illustration we give a short example in Appendix A.1.

For SNaive a seasonal component c is included. To predict one value we take the value of the same timepoint of the last known season in the data. This works iteratively.

$$\hat{Y}_{M,j} = \begin{cases} D_{M+j-c} & j \leq c \\ \hat{Y}_{M,j-c} & j > c \end{cases} \quad (j = 1, \dots, h; M = N, \dots, T - h) \quad (4)$$

In this formula again M is the timepoint up to that we assume to know the data, D the original data column for one feature and \hat{Y} the prediction matrix. We give a short example in Appendix A.2 for better illustration.

3.2 Performance measures

To evaluate the performance the scaled MSE and MAE are used. Z-score normalization is done for each feature. For that the training data is split again, at the cutpoint N_0 . From the start of the training set up to the cutpoint the mean μ_i and standard deviation σ_i for each feature i are calculated. The centered and scaled datacolumns are $S^i = \frac{D^i - \mu_i}{\sigma_i}$, where D^i is the datacolumn for feature i . After that the linear model is applied and we get the predictions \hat{Y}^i for the scaled input.

The following formula describes the MSE:

$$MSE = \frac{1}{H \cdot h \cdot d} \sum_{i=1}^d \sum_{j=1}^H \sum_{k=1}^h (S_{N-1+j+k}^i - \hat{Y}_{(N-1+j)_k}^i)^2 \quad (5)$$

The formula for the MAE looks like that:

$$MAE = \frac{1}{H \cdot h \cdot d} \sum_{i=1}^d \sum_{j=1}^H \sum_{k=1}^h |S_{N-1+j+k}^i - \hat{Y}_{(N-1+j)_k}^i| \quad (6)$$

3.3 Parameters

In Table 1 all used parameters of the paper [4] are shown. For each dataset the splits for splitting the data into train and test set are listed. Then all horizons for which the models are applied and the seasonal component for each dataset are given. The cutpoint column gives the cutpoint for the set of the training set which is used for normalization.

Table 1. Parameters

Datasets	Split	Window length	Horizons	Seasonality	Cutpoint
ETTh1	1-16/17-20 months	672	24/48/168/336/720	24/24/168/168/672	75/25%
ETTh2	1-16/17-20 months	672	24/48/168/336/720	24/24/168/168/672	75/25%
ETTh1	1-16/17-20 months	672	24/48/96/288/672	96	75/25%
ECL	80/20%	672	48/168/336/720/960	168	87.5/12.5%
WTH	80/20%	672	24/48/168/338/720	24	87.5/12.5%
Weather	80/20%	672	96/192/336/720	144	87.5/12.5%
ILI	80/20%	96	24/36/48/60	52	87.5/12.5%
Exchange	80/20%	31	96/192/336/720	1	87.5/12.5%

All datasets are splitted into 80% training data and 20 % test data, except the ETTh1 and ETTh2 which are splitted by the given months in the datasets into data about the first 16 months and the months 17-20. The seasonal component is mostly given by one number, otherwise the different seasonal components belong to the different horizons.

3.4 Results

In order to reproduce the paper we implemented the models and performance measures with the given parameters for all datasets except the ECL data, due to computational reasons. After that we generated the results in Table 2.

Table 2. Reproduced results

Dataset	ETTh1					ETTh2					ETTm1				
Horizon	24	48	168	336	720	24	48	168	336	720	24	48	96	288	672
SNaive MSE	0.407	0.464	0.737	0.751	0.7	0.315	0.388	0.747	0.832	0.814	0.409	0.418	0.421	0.504	0.613
SNaive MAE	0.366	0.394	0.535	0.55	0.556	0.331	0.378	0.571	0.625	0.618	0.366	0.374	0.377	0.417	0.473
Linear MSE	0.325	0.371	0.483	0.548	0.592	0.222	0.303	0.493	0.625	0.7	0.425	0.568	0.492	0.551	0.61
Linear MAE	0.358	0.38	0.443	0.487	0.523	0.302	0.357	0.47	0.552	0.601	0.4	0.486	0.448	0.484	0.519

Dataset	weather				ILI				exchange				WTH				
Horizon	96	192	336	720	24	36	48	60	96	192	336	720	24	48	168	336	720
SNaive MSE	0.313	0.34	0.381	0.442	2.487	2.217	2.101	1.903	0.079	0.165	0.304	0.807	0.574	0.682	0.842	0.905	0.959
SNaive MAE	0.285	0.303	0.33	0.369	0.966	0.932	0.921	0.923	0.193	0.286	0.396	0.675	0.449	0.513	0.604	0.64	0.673
Linear MSE	0.24	0.255	0.308	0.385	2.932	2.992	2.985	3.107	0.081	0.161	0.262	0.458	0.344	0.423	0.55	0.597	0.646
Linear MAE	0.312	0.327	0.368	0.42	1.123	1.146	1.145	1.172	0.199	0.286	0.378	0.533	0.377	0.443	0.538	0.571	0.605

The results which we get when we use the described models, measures, parameters and datasets (Table 2) are slightly different to those from the paper, which are shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Results from the paper

Dataset	ETTh1					ETTh2					ETTm1				
Horizon	24	48	168	336	720	24	48	168	336	720	24	48	96	288	672
SNaive MSE	0.424	0.465	0.656	0.683	0.65	0.266	0.322	0.578	0.567	0.55	0.168	0.168	0.188	0.225	0.282
SNaive MAE	0.389	0.407	0.509	0.52	0.518	0.304	0.339	0.483	0.491	0.488	0.269	0.269	0.287	0.315	0.353
Linear MSE	0.305	0.341	0.404	0.434	0.49	0.166	0.218	0.323	0.386	0.665	0.09	0.121	0.162	0.261	0.364
Linear MAE	0.357	0.379	0.422	0.445	0.501	0.261	0.299	0.374	0.419	0.549	0.185	0.219	0.253	0.325	0.394

Dataset	weather				ILI				exchange				WTH				
Horizon	96	192	336	720	24	36	48	60	96	192	336	720	24	48	168	336	720
SNaive MSE	0.317	0.343	0.383	0.443	2.564	2.266	2.142	1.917	0.081	0.167	0.306	0.81	0.599	0.698	0.848	0.908	0.96
SNaive MAE	0.288	0.305	0.331	0.37	1.004	0.957	0.941	0.939	0.196	0.289	0.398	0.676	0.468	0.525	0.608	0.642	0.674
Linear MSE	0.139	0.181	0.229	0.295	2.168	2.233	2.277	2.353	0.082	0.166	0.282	0.576	0.323	0.391	0.5	0.543	0.602
Linear MAE	0.2	0.244	0.288	0.341	0.97	1.015	1.040	1.067	0.2	0.292	0.395	0.604	0.361	0.42	0.504	0.534	0.572

4 DIFFICULTIES

In this chapter we summarize all difficulties which occurred when we tried to reproduce the paper and how we handled those.

4.1 Model formulation

When reading the paper the main idea is understandable and interesting results are stated. When we took a closer look at the model formulation, it was not clear to us, how this model should work. Equation (1) of the paper was defined as the following:

$$\hat{x}_{j,n+i} = \theta_{j,1}x_{j,1} + \dots + \theta_{j,n}x_{j,n} \quad (i = 1, \dots, h, j = 1, \dots, d) \quad (7)$$

where $\theta_{j,1}, \dots, \theta_{j,n}$ are the parameters to be learned and $(x_{j,1}, \dots, x_{j,n})$ is the j -th dimension of the input matrix. Since this formula does not depend on i , it seems to us, that every prediction $\hat{x}_{j,n+i}$ gets the same value for fixed j

and n , which is written differently in the text.

Because of this confusion, we got in contact with the author, to clarify the idea of the linear regression. As an answer we got a description of the idea for the linear model, which uses the sliding window method. This method is described in Section 3.1.

4.2 Performance measures

After taking a closer look on the performance measures, the formulas for the MSE and MAE seem not right to us. The measures in the paper are defined as the following:

$$MSE = \frac{1}{H \cdot d} \sum_{i=1}^d \sum_{j=1}^H \left(\frac{X_{i,j} - \mu_i}{\sigma_i} - \hat{X}_{i,j} \right)^2 \quad (8)$$

$$MAE = \frac{1}{H \cdot d} \sum_{i=1}^d \sum_{j=1}^H \left| \frac{X_{i,j} - \mu_i}{\sigma_i} - \hat{X}_{i,j} \right| \quad (9)$$

where $X_{i,j} = \{x_{i,N+j+1}, \dots, x_{i,N+j+h}\}$ and $\hat{X}_{i,j} = \{\hat{x}_{i,N+j+1}, \dots, \hat{x}_{i,N+j+h}\}$.

The results of the formulas are vectors and not numbers. Furthermore, we do not understand how and when the normalization is done in the formula. Since the author confirmed that the formulas are not exactly right, but we do not have enough time to wait for further information, we believe that another formula is used in the paper. We then used formulas for the MSE (equation (5)) and MAE (equation (6)) which make most sense to us after considering different possibilities.

4.3 Results

One difficulty for us was that no code is available online and that the datasets were not directly linked. Therefore, we needed to implement everything on our own to be able to compare the results. We did not get the same results, which probably is the case, since we formulated the model and the performance measures differently than described in the paper, because of the difficulties we described previously. Moreover, we still do not know how they ended up with their results, because we tried different versions of the performance measures, tried adding an intercept and scaled at different stages and never got the same results. Another issue is that the paper states the results of other deep learning methods in their tables, which they took from other papers they referenced, but the values are mostly different. Because of this, we do not know if they reproduced everything from the other papers and used their own definition of the MSE and MAE or how these values were generated.

5 CONCLUSION

We tried to reproduce the paper "Do Simpler Statistical Methods Perform Better in Multivariate Long Sequence Time-Series Forecasting?" [4]. Although a lot of information about the experimental setup in the paper as well as the code were missing, we were able to produce similar results to those in the paper. For that purpose we reformulated the models and the performance measures and implemented the models from scratch. However, even if we got similar results, we cannot fully confirm the results of the paper. In order to be able to come to the same conclusion, that linear regression and SNaive are performing better than deep learning methods in multivariate long sequence time-series forecasting, we would have to reproduce the results of the other papers, which state the results of the deep learning methods, with our parameters and performance measures.

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A APPENDIX: EXAMPLES

A.1 Example One: Linear Regression

We give a short example for the linear regression model, which should illustrate how our model works. We choose the size of the dataset $T = 15$, the train data length $N = 10$, the horizon $h = 2$ and the timesteps we use to predict $n = 3$. Therefore we get a data matrix X with dimension $(N - n - (h - 1)) \times n = 6 \times 3$ and the target matrix Y with dimension $(N - n - (h - 1)) \times h = 6 \times 2$. When we apply the linear regression with this model matrices we get the model coefficients θ_1 and θ_2 , each with dimension $n = 3$. Those are multiplied on the predictions input and from that the predictions \hat{Y} are produced, which have the dimension $H \times h = (T - N) - (h - 1) \times h = 4 \times 2$.

A.2 Example Two: SNaive

We give a short example for the SNaive model, which should illustrate how our model works. We choose the size of the dataset $T = 11$, the train data length $N = 6$, the horizon $h = 4$ and the seasonality is $c = 3$, which means there are three different parts in a season.

